

Circular Water Futures: Evaluating Rainwater Harvesting Compliance and Treated Greywater Reuse, Marappanpalya (Ward 44), Bengaluru

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BWSSB	:	Bengaluru Water Supply and Sewerage Board
BBMP	:	Bruhat Bengaluru Mahanagara Palike
KSCST	:	Karnataka State Council for Science & Technology
CMDA	:	Chennai Metropolitan Development Authority
CMWSSB	:	Chennai Metropolitan Water Supply and Sewerage Board
CGWB	:	Central Ground Water Board
NMCG	:	National Mission for Clean Ganga
CEEW	:	Council on Energy, Environment and Water
CPCB	:	Central Pollution Control Board
PIB	:	Press Information Bureau
SANDRP	:	South Asia Network on Dams, Rivers and People
IMD	:	India Meteorological Department
KSAPCC	:	Karnataka State Action Plan on Climate Change
IRWM	:	Integrated Water Resources Management
RWH	:	Rainwater Harvesting
WHO	:	World Health Organisation
STPs	:	Sewage Treatment Plants
ML	:	Million Litres
MLD	:	Million Litres per Day
GIS	:	Geographic Information System
NGO	:	Non-Governmental Organisation

ABSTRACT

Bengaluru is facing water stress due to the combined pressures of rapid urbanisation, groundwater depletion, and uneven governance of urban water resources. This study examines the potential of rainwater harvesting (RWH) and treated greywater reuse to strengthen water circularity at the ward level. Marappanpalya or Ward number 44 is the focus of this study. A Geospatial Compliance Assessment using satellite imagery indicated that while a substantial share of rooftops are technically suitable for harvesting, less than half comply with existing mandates. Scenario-based estimates suggest that even partial improvements in compliance could contribute to the enhancement of water inflows. Scenario modelling of greywater flows, adapted from the Urban Metabolism Water Mass Balance Framework, demonstrates that treated greywater could supply a considerable share of non-potable needs, thus reducing dependence on external sources. A comparative review of policy regimes in Bengaluru and Chennai further reveals that weak enforcement and limited institutional coordination remain the primary constraints. The findings highlight the importance of integrated governance, stronger monitoring, and citizen engagement in scaling decentralised solutions. Advancements in RWH and treated greywater reuse can together play a decisive role in reshaping Bengaluru's urban water governance towards circularity.

Keywords: Rainwater Harvesting, Treated Greywater Reuse, Water Circularity, Urban Governance, Geospatial Compliance Assessment, Scenario Modelling

Introduction

Bengaluru is the capital city of Karnataka, which has historical and socio-economic significance. It is located on the Karnataka plateau, geographically a water-scarce region. It has depended on wells and lakes for its water requirements. It is one of the fastest-growing cities in India with an increasing population of 13 million (Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, 2011).

The city has faced water scarcity in recent years due to rapid urbanisation, climate change, and unsustainable water resource management. Bengaluru has lost 66% of its forest and 74% of its lakes and rivers, which has resulted in groundwater depletion and increased vulnerability to droughts (Banerjee, 2024). Cauvery River supplies around 70% of drinking water needs, and it is under stress due to uneven rainfall patterns and unplanned city expansion that disrupts the hydrological balance of the city (Banerjee, 2024). The population of the city has tripled since 1990, augmenting pressure on natural resources. The Bengaluru Water Supply and Sewerage Board (BWSSB) provides 1,450 million litres of water daily for consumption; however, this falls short of the city's demand of 2,100 million litres (Banerjee, 2024). Climate change is going to exacerbate this water crisis. There is high spatial and inter-annual variability in rainfall, and instances of extreme rainfall events have increased in the past decades. The temperature has risen by an average of 0.6°C. Projections indicate a further increase of 1.7°C to 2.2°C by the 2030s, which will shift the rainfall patterns and make water supply more unpredictable (Karnataka State Action Plan on Climate Change, 2012). Similarly, drought incidences are expected to rise by up to 10% by 2050, which will create challenges to water accessibility (Karnataka State Action Plan on Climate Change, 2012).

To address these challenges, the government of Karnataka has introduced many guidelines. According to the Bangalore Water Supply and Sewerage (BWSS) (Amendment) Act 2016, RWH is mandatory for all new buildings and those with a site area exceeding 216 square meters (approximately 2,325 square feet). The State Water Policy 2022 promotes Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), encouraging RWH, wastewater recycling, and groundwater recharge across households, apartments, public spaces, and industrial sectors. To ensure compliance, the state government has introduced penalties and enforcement mechanisms.

Objectives

This background gives context to this research, which provides the following objectives:

1. To evaluate the supply and demand dynamics of water in Bengaluru and assess the role of RWH in bridging the city's urban water gap.
2. To estimate greywater generation and assess the potential of greywater reuse in supplementing Bengaluru's urban water supply.
3. To critically evaluate the design and implementation of RWH policies in Bengaluru through a comparative policy analysis with Chennai.

Methodology

For the first objective, a Geospatial Compliance Assessment was conducted to estimate the implementation of RWH in the Marappanpalya Ward (currently also identified as Ward 44, N.B. ward numbers and boundaries are subject to change over time), Bengaluru, as there is a lack of official ward-level data on this. This method constituted the use of high-resolution satellite imagery via Google Earth Pro to manually identify rooftop-based RWH infrastructure such as storage tanks, downpipes, recharge pits, and sump connections. Buildings with a site area exceeding 2,160 sq. ft. (approximately 216 sq. meters) were included in the assessment, since, according to the BWSS(Amendment) Act, 2016, RWH is mandatory for such buildings. The ruler tool in Google Earth Pro was used to measure rooftop dimensions, and buildings with areas exceeding approximately 14.7 meters \times 14.7 meters were selected. A purposive sample of over 50 residential and non-residential buildings was taken.

To estimate greywater generation and assess the potential of greywater reuse in Ward 44, this study adopted the Urban Metabolism Water Mass Balance Framework, originally developed by Kenway et al. (2011) and later refined for the Indian context by Paul et al. (2018). This framework conceptualises cities as living organisms and quantifies the inflow, use, and outflow of resources such as water, energy, and waste across a defined urban boundary. However, this framework was adapted to explore greywater dynamics rather than the entire urban water system. The original model integrates precipitation, river inflows, stormwater, and groundwater recharge, while the tailored version isolates the wastewater component, focusing on the generation, treatment, and reuse of greywater. And to calculate the demand,

the data related to daily water consumption was considered, for which the average of the water supply of April, May, and June 2025 was taken, as data is available for these months only, and water is also in peak demand during this time. The study used datasets from BWSSB and the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) to estimate key variables, including total sewage generated, the share treated in STPs, and the volume of water reused for non-potable purposes.

To operationalise this adapted framework, the study employed a custom-designed greywater reuse flow diagram (Figure 1) originally developed by Paul et al (2018) in the context of Bengaluru city. The figure maps the sub-flows within the urban water system specific to greywater. This begins with the domestic water supply, which is split into blackwater and greywater. Then it divides the grey water flow into treated and untreated. After this, it traces the greywater flow into centralised and decentralised STPs. The model then explains the flow of greywater through three distinct pathways as shown in Figure 1. Then treated greywater is further routed into three primary reuse applications: toilet flushing, gardening and landscaping, and other institutional or domestic reuse streams. Using this structure, the study quantifies the current level of reuse and then simulates three hypothetical reuse scenarios (30%, 50%, and 75%) to estimate reductions in freshwater demand. These projections are based on available literature and secondary data from BWSSB and other published studies.

Figure 1 Custom-designed greywater reuse flow diagram

This study limits itself to exploring total non-potable reuse potential through cumulative scenarios. Application categories are included to illustrate the range of end-uses for treated greywater.

And finally, to critically evaluate the policy framework governing RWH in Bengaluru, this study adopted a comparative policy analysis approach. The analysis was focused on assessing the design, implementation, and effectiveness of RWH mandates in the city and was benchmarked against Chennai, which implemented RWH policy citywide in 2003 and is widely cited as a successful model of decentralized water governance in India (Centre for Science and Environment, n.d.).

The evaluation in Bengaluru was drawn from a set of key regulatory documents, which include the Guidelines on RWH, the BWSS(Amendment) Act, the State Water Policy, and KSAPCC. These documents were analysed to extract provisions related to mandatory coverage, design specifications, enforcement mechanisms, and institutional responsibilities. Then, a comparative matrix was developed to examine policy variables across Bengaluru and Chennai under the following parameters:

1. Mandate year and scope
2. Enforcement mechanisms (penalties, inspections, regularisation)
3. Institutional roles and monitoring frameworks

4. Incentives/subsidies or citizen engagement strategies
5. Reported implementation levels (coverage, compliance, enforcement challenges)

This matrix allows for a structured analysis of what has worked in Chennai versus the current bottlenecks in Bengaluru's implementation pathway. The study was drawn from secondary sources such as media reports, urban policy evaluations, and academic publications to triangulate official claims with ground realities.

Findings

While the BWSS (Amendment) Act, 2016 applies to residential buildings above 216 m², this study also included large non-residential structures such as warehouses to assess the broader technical potential of rooftop rainwater harvesting in Ward 44. Compliance results, therefore, mix statutory obligations (residential) with voluntary opportunities (non-residential), and should be interpreted accordingly. 50 buildings were assessed through geospatial inspection using Google Earth Pro. Each building was categorised into three compliance statuses: compliant (presence of visible RWH infrastructure, such as downpipes and overhead tanks), non-compliant (absence of discernible RWH features), and unclear (cases where visual confirmation was hindered by shadows or vegetation). The results reveal that 20 buildings (40 percent) were compliant, 14 buildings (28 percent) were non-compliant, and 16 buildings (32 percent) fell into the unclear category (Figure 2). It is important to note that three compliant buildings were below the statutory plot-size threshold, which reflects instances of voluntary adoption beyond legal mandates.

Figure 2 Compliance status of RWH mandate (in numbers out of 50 buildings analysed)

To complement the graphical representation, the spatial distribution of compliance is presented in Figure 3, which shows the geospatial patterns of adoption within Ward 44. This spatial perspective highlights both areas of concentrated adoption and clusters where mandated structures appear absent.

Figure 3 GIS-based analysis of RWH compliance in Ward 44

While the geospatial method provides a cost-effective and scalable proxy for compliance monitoring, it has certain limitations. Rooftop imagery cannot confirm the operational status of tanks or pipes, detect underground recharge pits, or account for systems concealed within the built structure. Tree canopy, building shadows, and image resolution constraints create uncertainty, which is reflected in the sizable “unclear” category. However, the combined

spatial and statistical analysis offers valuable insights into patterns of uptake and highlights where enforcement efforts or awareness campaigns may be most needed.

The potential annual rooftop rainwater yield for Ward 44 was estimated using the standard volumetric formula:

$$\text{Annual Yield} = A \times R \times C$$

where A is the effective rooftop area (m^2), R is the mean annual rainfall (1.0778 m for Bengaluru Urban, based on IMD 1991-2020 climatological normal), and C is the runoff coefficient (0.8 for impervious concrete roofs). On this basis, each square metre of rooftop is expected to yield approximately 0.862 m^3 per year. Aggregating across the 50 assessed buildings, the total potential harvest was estimated at 69.07 million litres (ML) per year (Appendix 1).

A scenario analysis was undertaken to compare current levels of adoption with a hypothetical full compliance situation:

Table 1 Scenario analysis to compare adoption levels

Compliance Scenario	Monthly Potential (ML)	Annual Potential (ML)
Current	1.97	23.66
50 percent	2.88	34.54
75 percent	4.32	51.8
Full	5.76	69.07

Note: Compliance range reflects variation in per-household water demand estimates.

As shown in Table 1, currently compliant buildings contribute 23.66 ML annually, which represents just over one-third of the ward’s total potential. A scenario of 50% compliance would increase the harvest to 34.54 ML annually, while 75% compliance could yield 51.80 ML. At full compliance, all 50 eligible buildings in Ward 44 could together harvest up to 69.07 ML annually, substantially easing estimated household water demand. These figures highlight that even partial improvements in compliance can deliver meaningful gains for urban water security.

The monthly water consumption for April, May, and June 2025 averages around 126.13 million litres (ML) per month. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) (2006), greywater constitutes around 60 per cent of the total wastewater, which amounts to 75.68 ML per month. Hernandez Leal et al. (2010) report that greywater can account for up to 75% of the total household wastewater volume, which equates to about 94.60 ML per month.

Integrating both estimates, greywater in total constitutes around 60-75% of the total household wastewater stream in Ward No. 44.

This greywater either goes to treatment sites or is left untreated. In the absence of ward-level data on greywater treatment ratio, this study is taking city-wide estimates as assumed figures for the amount of greywater treated in Ward 44. According to the National Mission for Clean Ganga (NMCG) state report, the city-wide sewage treatment ratio is approximately 44%. Greywater comprises bath, kitchen, and laundry effluent, which, as discussed above, is 60-75 percent. This implies that about 26-33 percent of the greywater generated across the ward is actually treated.

The treatment happens through either centralised Sewage Treatment Plants (STPs) or decentralised STPs. As a result, BWSSB has made it mandatory for apartments with 120 or more flats to establish wastewater treatment units (Bangalore Mirror, 2024). Apart from this, the city has over 3,000 decentralized STPs treating 615 million litres per day (MLD) (Citizen Matters, 2023).

In order to contextualize the spatial infrastructure available for greywater treatment, this study includes GIS-based visualizations of Ward 44 and its surroundings. Major STPs data is taken from BWSSB, which is then integrated with the Ward 44 boundary using QGIS for the nearest major STPs around it.

Figure 4 Ward 44 boundary

Figure 4 displays the spatial extent of Ward No. 44, Bengaluru, highlighting the internal road network and residential layout. It provides a detailed visual context of the ward where greywater generation and reuse potential are being estimated.

Figure 5 Nearest STPs to Ward 44

This map (Figure 5) spatially locates Ward 44 in relation to its nearest operational STPs in Mailasandra, Kadabeesanahalli, and Rajacanal. The proximity to these facilities supports the rationale for applying city-wide average treatment ratios (26–33%) to Ward 44, due to potential connectivity and infrastructural integration.

After treatment, the treated water is used for toilet flushing, gardening, landscaping, car washing, floor cleaning, and even general cleaning and laundry at the household level, especially in apartments with dual plumbing systems. Apart from this, large-scale applications of treated greywater include irrigation and agriculture, public landscaping and parks, industrial uses, lake rejuvenation, and groundwater recharge. Initiatives such as the Koramangala-Challaghatta (KC) Valley Project show how treated greywater can be channelled for agricultural use and aquifer replenishment in water-stressed regions (Down To Earth, 2023).

As outlined in Figure 1, the adaptation of the Urban Metabolism Water Mass Balance Framework developed by Paul et al. (2018), the research evaluates reuse potential across varying treatment and adoption scenarios.

Table 2 Scenario modelling of potential reuse

Treated Source	Treated water (ML) per month	Reuse @ 30% (ML)	Reuse @ 50% (ML)	Reuse @ 75% (ML)
26% of 60%	19.68	5.9	9.84	14.76

33% of 60%	24.97	7.49	12.49	18.73
26% of 75%	24.59	7.38	12.3	18.45
33% of 75%	31.22	9.36	15.61	23.41

The first column in Table 2 specifies the proportion of greywater treated expressed as a combination of the assumed city-wide sewage treatment ratio (26 percent or 33 percent) and the estimated share of greywater in total household wastewater (60 percent or 75 percent). In the case of 26 percent of 60 percent, approximately 19.68 ML of greywater is treated monthly. This treated volume is then modelled across three hypothetical reuse adoption scenarios, that is, 30 percent, 50 percent, and 75 percent, yielding potential reuse volumes of 5.9 ML, 9.84 ML, and 14.76 ML, respectively. Similarly, for the 33 percent of 75 percent scenario, where 31.22 ML is treated, the reuse potential rises to 9.36 ML at 30 percent adoption, 15.61 ML at 50 percent adoption, and 23.41 ML at 75 percent adoption. This illustrates that higher treatment ratios, coupled with greater adoption of reuse practices, significantly increase the availability of treated greywater for non-potable applications.

Bengaluru and Chennai are metropolitan cities of South India and share comparable urban, climatic, and economic profiles that give rationale for comparing the policy framework. Geographically, both lie in the monsoon belt and receive rainfall from the southwest and northeast monsoons, though annual precipitation varies significantly. Bengaluru receives about 986 mm (Citizen Matters, 2021) compared to Chennai's 1,382 mm (Blue Green Atlas, 2010). Their demographic scale is similar, with Chennai's metropolitan population at 8.65 million and Bengaluru's urban agglomeration at 8.50 million as per the 2011 Census. Central Ground Water Board (CGWB) monitoring shows that most metro-area wells declined by 0-2 meters post-monsoon over 2010-2019, with pockets in Chennai exceeding 4 meters declines (Press Information Bureau (PIB), 2021), while a city-specific study in Bengaluru reports declines of 5-15 meters across urban limits and up to 20-25 meters in peri-urban villages between 2003 and 2016 (South Asia Network on Dams, Rivers and People (SANDRP), 2025).

Figure 6 gives the RWH policy background for both cities.

Comparing RWH Mandates in Bengaluru and Chennai

Figure 6 Policy Basics (Source: BWSSB, CMWSSB)

In Bengaluru, enforcement is driven by the BWSSB through penalties and disconnection. BWSSB does a periodic audit of its water meter connections and bills defaulters. Regulations allow the Board to levy extra charges; residential defaulters pay an extra 25% of the water bill for 3 months and 50% thereafter, while commercial properties pay 50% then 100%. (Urban Waters, 2023). Fines are collected monthly as part of the utility bill. The 2011 rules also permit cutting off water supply for non-compliance, though in practice, this is less common than surcharges. Chennai's approach emphasised regulatory enforcement over direct financial incentives to individual property owners. While the state funded some public RWH infrastructure projects (Chennai Corporation, 2015), the primary strategy relied on mandatory compliance backed by service disconnection threats rather than subsidies or rebates for private installations (Citizen Matters, 2017).

Bengaluru’s RWH framework is overseen by the BWSSB and supported by the Karnataka State Council for Science & Technology (KSCST). The law and BWSSB regulations assign the Board to “provide rainwater harvesting structure,” etc., meaning it issues notifications, inspects compliance, and levies penalties (The BWSS Act, 1964). BWSSB reportedly tracks installations via its billing database and periodic surveys. The Board’s recent initiatives include setting up an AI -driven groundwater task force (with IISc, CGWB, etc.) to monitor groundwater levels and incentivise recharge (Down to Earth, 2024). However, data gaps remain. BWSSB admits it does not even know all the older properties in its jurisdiction that should have RWH, and other agencies (BBMP/city planning) have a limited role as building approvals historically focused more on sewage than RWH (Citizen Matters, 2023).

In Chennai, multiple agencies coordinate RWH. The Chennai Metropolitan Water Supply & Sewerage Board (CMWSSB) and Chennai Metropolitan Development Authority (CMDA) enforce the building plan requirement. It was strengthened by the active involvement of non-governmental actors, as NGOs and civil society organisations played a key role in driving momentum and ensuring the installation of effective RWH systems that captured rain and recharged groundwater (Vivek, 2016). The city government also maintained a monitoring cell for RWH under CMDA to inspect installations, though by recent accounts, this oversight has weakened (Down to Earth, 2024). Overall, RWH in Chennai has been mainstreamed into the urban governance apparatus, whereas in Bengaluru it remains largely the BWSSB’s domain, as explained in Figure 7.

Comparing rainwater harvesting governance across two Indian cities

Figure 7 RWH Governance Comparison across Bengaluru and Chennai

The actual implementation of Bengaluru’s rainwater harvesting mandate is far less than what is outlined on paper. According to BWSSB data, only about 1.9 lakh properties with water

connections have installed RWH systems, out of approximately 10.8 lakh connections, reflecting a compliance rate of 18 percent (Figure 8, Citizen Matters, 2023). Compliance among government and public-sector buildings remains limited, with around 11 percent meeting the requirement (Times of India, 2024). Out of an estimated 50 lakh structures in Bengaluru, only 2 lakhs have RWH (4 percent) (Times of India, 2024). BWSSB acknowledges that its data underrepresents the actual scope of the mandate, as monitoring has largely focused on buildings situated on 60x40 ft (existing) and 30x40 ft (new) sites, leaving older structures and those in peripheral areas unaccounted for (Citizen Matters, 2023). Thus, a significant proportion of Bengaluru’s residential and commercial properties that fall within the statutory threshold remain outside the purview of enforcement.

In contrast, the actual implementation of rainwater harvesting in Chennai has been far more extensive. Following the 2003 mandate, a large proportion of new multi-storey apartments and institutional buildings incorporated RWH systems, with early assessments crediting the city with being “much better off in fresh water availability” due to the combination of strict policy enforcement and active citizen participation (Vivek, 2016). However, recent analyses highlight challenges in sustaining this momentum, as many apartment complexes lack adequate maintenance of their RWH installations, and both public interest and enforcement have gradually declined (Down To Earth, 2024). Chennai’s per-capita compliance continues to surpass that of Bengaluru, with estimates for targeted buildings 68-75 percent (Citizen Matters, 2023).

*Figure 8
RWH
Compliance
in Bengaluru
and Chennai*

Thus, the above analysis shows major policy gaps in

Bengaluru’s RWH implementation, which can be strengthened by taking various policy measures as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 9 Measures for effective RWH implementation

Figure 9 outlines the sequential steps required for implementing effective Rainwater Harvesting (RWH) and how both cities can learn from each other’s best practices. It begins with data collection, which provides the foundation for understanding existing systems. This must be followed by consistent enforcement of regulations, incentives and support to encourage adoption. Institutional coordination across agencies and public awareness campaigns is essential to create shared responsibility.

Discussion

The evaluation of supply and demand dynamics in Ward 44 demonstrates that the current level of RWH adoption remains limited, despite the presence of a legal framework mandating installation for larger buildings. This outcome corresponds with the Guidelines on Rainwater Harvesting issued by BWSSB (2015), which recognise that enforcement is uneven and dependent on periodic inspections that often fail to capture the true extent of compliance. Reports in recent years confirm that although penalties are being collected from non-compliant households, the broader scale of adoption remains well below potential, and point out structural challenges in monitoring and governance (Times of India, 2025).

These limitations become more concerning when viewed against the context of greywater management. The Ward-level scenario modelling undertaken in the study indicates that treated greywater reuse could reduce freshwater demand if appropriate treatment and distribution systems are effectively implemented. The Council on Energy, Environment and Water (CEEW) report in 2023 notes that treated wastewater can substitute for non-potable demand, especially in sectors such as landscaping, toilet flushing, and industry.

The question of how such practices can be effectively institutionalised requires turning to the policy framework. The comparative analysis between Bengaluru and Chennai emphasises that the effectiveness of RWH policies is shaped by both statutory mandates as well as institutional design and citizen participation. National guidelines, such as the Toolkit for Preparing City Action Plans for Reuse of Treated Used Water (NMCG, 2023), underscore that successful implementation requires structured planning, inter-agency coordination, and participatory engagement of stakeholders. While Bengaluru's regulations are comprehensive on paper, enforcement has remained primarily with the BWSSB, with limited integration of other urban governance institutions. In contrast, Chennai's experience illustrates the value of wider institutional involvement, as both the CMWSSB and civil society actors played active roles in embedding RWH into the urban landscape.

Thus, the findings across all objectives point to the interconnected nature of urban water governance. Limited compliance with RWH reduces the immediate availability of supplementary water, while inadequate integration of treated greywater reuse curtails opportunities to diversify supply sources. Both of these are shaped by the policy framework, which in Bengaluru remains fragmented despite formal provisions. Strengthening implementation will therefore require moving beyond technical mandates to create institutional arrangements that encourage compliance, enable treated wastewater reuse, and build sustained citizen engagement.

Conclusion

The analysis of Ward 44 illustrates that RWH and treated greywater reuse can help in advancements in urban water circularity. RWH at the building level and the reintroduction of treated wastewater into non-potable uses can extend the lifecycle of water within the city. The potential contribution of these practices can augment water supply and reduce the pressure on groundwater and piped infrastructure. Thus, they represent complementary strategies that could mitigate the water deficit in Bengaluru and contribute to a more resilient and

sustainable urban water regime. However, the limited compliance with existing mandates, coupled with the uneven integration of treated greywater reuse, underscores that the transition toward circularity remains constrained by governance gaps rather than technical feasibility.

This study carries certain limitations that shape its findings. The geospatial survey was based on only fifty buildings, which makes the results less generalisable. Without field checks, the compliance figures remain indicative rather than conclusive. Greywater estimates also relied on secondary data and assumptions. Water consumption was averaged over three summer months, and city-wide figures were applied at the ward level, which risks overlooking local variations. The policy comparison between Bengaluru and Chennai faced similar gaps, as the insights came from government documents and secondary studies rather than official monitoring records or interviews.

Future research should address these shortcomings through primary data collection. Household-level surveys and field-based checks could verify satellite observations and also highlight behavioural factors like awareness, costs, and maintenance practices. Collaborating with BWSSB, BBMP, and ward offices would improve access to disaggregated datasets and strengthen ward-level monitoring. Ground validation of geospatial methods through on-site inspections would also make compliance assessments more accurate when scaled city-wide.

The scope of analysis can be expanded to include stakeholder perspectives. Engaging with residents' associations, NGOs, and utility officials can reveal barriers such as poor awareness, weak enforcement, or inadequate upkeep of systems. Methodologically, combining compliance data with hydrological modelling would allow estimates of how RWH and greywater reuse contribute to groundwater recharge over time. A longitudinal approach that tracks adoption and enforcement trends would provide deeper insights into policy effectiveness and citizen participation.

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Appendix

Name	Area (in square meters)	Annual_yield_m3	Annual_yield_ML
B01	5220	4500.8928	4.5008928
B02	6194	5340.71456	5.34071456
B03	1788	1541.68512	1.54168512
B04	2246	1936.59104	1.93659104
B05	1523	1313.19152	1.31319152
B06	2317	1997.81008	1.99781008
B07	2716	2341.84384	2.34184384
B08	3398	2929.89152	2.92989152
B09	3072	2648.80128	2.64880128
B10	1355	1168.3352	1.1683352

B11	611	526.82864	0.52682864
B12	746	643.23104	0.64323104
B13	613	528.55312	0.52855312
B14	1293	1114.87632	1.11487632
B15	857	738.93968	0.73893968
B16	437	376.79888	0.37679888
B17	485	418.1864	0.4181864
B18	1335	1151.0904	1.1510904
B19	1679	1447.70096	1.44770096
B20	1770	1526.1648	1.5261648
B21	1501	1294.22224	1.29422224
B22	4320	3724.8768	3.7248768
B23	5608	4835.44192	4.83544192
B24	3676	3169.59424	3.16959424
B25	2463	2123.69712	2.12369712
B26	4430	3819.7232	3.8197232
B27	1299	1120.04976	1.12004976
B28	1499	1292.49776	1.29249776
B29	366	315.57984	0.31557984
B30	731	630.29744	0.63029744
B31	173	149.16752	0.14916752
B32	161	138.82064	0.13882064
B33	295	254.3608	0.2543608
B34	322	277.64128	0.27764128
B35	1297	1118.32528	1.11832528
B36	1079	930.35696	0.93035696
B37	2751	2372.02224	2.37202224
B38	1729	1490.81296	1.49081296
B39	1128	972.60672	0.97260672
B40	2157	1859.85168	1.85985168
B41	191	164.68784	0.16468784
B42	217	187.10608	0.18710608
B43	364	313.85536	0.31385536
B44	354	305.23296	0.30523296
B45	339	292.29936	0.29229936
B46	390	336.2736	0.3362736
B47	463	399.21712	0.39921712
B48	426	367.31424	0.36731424
B49	331	285.40144	0.28540144
B50	389	335.41136	0.33541136
Total			69.06887296

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